

Radar Charts and Equilibrium Series to Control Ageing Defined Mathematically

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Abstract:- This paper is determined to relation between equilibrium and how the radar chart plots equilibrium. Now why equilibrium? The concept behind equilibrium is to control ageing in humans so that the span of life increases. This is a mathematical expression of how ageing would be controlled in terms of radar charts. I hope this paper serves as a first step towards decoding immortality mathematically. I do not consider this attempt of mine insane. Nothing is impossible or abstract. Would appreciate feedback on this paper and continuation of research in this topic.

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I. INTRODUCTION

This paper intends to find out how the process of ageing [4][1] can be brought to equilibrium stage. Natural ageing is irreversible. It is like a sine wave but does not continue. It ends at a point. If we can make the ageing process constant we will live longer. If suppose we stop the ageing process at around 30 year age for humans, we will live longer. This is the mathematical representation of such an attempt.

A. Sine wave series

We have a sine wave series as follows:

Fig. 1: Sine wave plotted in line graph

A series $= (1, 2, 1, 0, \{1\}, 2, 1, 0, 1)$ where "1" is the overlapping point of 2 sine waves.[7] "x" is shared as well as independent. If we consider "x" to be a centroid of a circle, its incorrect cause centroids do not have values or do not change. "x" is a constant / equilibrium value. Question is how can we intersect equilibrium to phase 2. "x" is inevitable in all points be it independent, augmented, depreciated and overlapping. Question is, what is x? There are 9 non-overlapping points. There are 3 unique values involving "x" or "y" in each. If I add a 10th point =R, now we have R points [2] 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9, R is an increment $9+1=R$

If the series is 1,1,1,1,1,1,1,1,1 it is growth depreciation. If "x" is a constant value=our current age=1. The 5th element overlaps, so how is the pentagon related? (this is only for sine wave, there can be many other patterns) The 5th element overlaps -its both wave and particle(an assumption)

B. Multiplication of 2 sine waves =2 but if its discrete=No of sine waves
Division is how would you divide continuity? We don't know currently.

As per A.O.Salman's [7], Radar chart plotted with coordinates in sine wave:

Fig. 2: Pattern of 1st coordinates of sine wave plotted in radar graph

Pattern of vibration is leaf-like. Its a pentagon.

Maybe we are wrong. Maybe someone has already made human life span=100 years. I want to make it 200 years[4].

C. 2 sine waves give an infinity pattern in a radar graph

If we go by Pongswatd and Smerpitak [6], we derive the following graphs:

Fig. 3: Sine waves plotted in radar graph with and without repetition

D. 3 sine waves give the below pattern: Infinithree

Fig. 4: Pattern created in radar graph with 3 sine waves

Question is why is the attempt to gain equilibrium through displacement leaf-like?

But 1 sine wave looks like our lungs in the radar graph.

Infinity is not 1, there can be discrete infinities. That doesn't serve our purpose though. Leaves aren't lives.

E. 4 sine waves==give 2 infinities/ 4 leaves/a flower/ a clock / infinifour

a	1
b	2
a	1
c	0
a	1
b	2
a	1
c	0
a	1
b	2
a	1
c	0
a	1
b	2
a	1
c	0

Fig. 5: Pattern created in radar graph with 4 sine waves

F. 5 sine waves give a flower but this is a good dial of a clock

a	1
b	2
a	1
c	0
a	1
b	2
a	1
c	0
a	1
b	2
a	1
c	0
a	1
b	2
a	1
c	0

Fig. 6: Pattern created in radar graph with 5 sine waves

G. 6 sine waves

Fig. 7: Pattern created in radar graph with 7 sine waves

H. 7 sine waves=7 flower petals or a 7 dialed clock and so on.
 9 Structure of eye is discrete

Fig. 8: Structure of eye created in radar graph with random coordinates

Even single value can be closed. Then question is what is increase in discrete values.

Fig. 9: Single value plotted in radar graph

I. Differences found when there is no overlap in the series A and the series B plotted in radar graph

Fig. 10: Difference between sine wave coordinates and random coordinates in radar graph

In the 1st figure there are 8 points from graph A of the sine wave without the 5th point “1”. 1st figure is plotted in radar graph[3].

In the 2nd figure I have replaced the points “0” with “1” of the 1st graph. Then if we divide the graph as [121, 1,121, 1], and take the square roots of each coordinate, we get [11,1,11,1]which when added gives =24 =a day [5].

Everything discrete is closed too, which means everything discrete is repetitive or can create loops. Question is whether null too is closed and repetitive?

Another question is how would we trigger a repetition in a discrete pattern? Why would we do it? To continue maybe [5].

Instead of spinning this thing has traversed from the value to the same point inside the set of concentric circles. Because it forgets or has memory? It hates changes. It tends to be independent.

II. SINGLE VALUE

Single value in a radar graph means that it tends to return back to where it started from like the sun does but it hasn't started moving yet.

I want to move a single value. We can't move a unit of some quantity. But it did move once to reach where it started from. What triggered the move? The concentric circles are moving too, maybe. We don't know much about space, currently.

Fig. 11: Ideal radar graph with single value

III. CONCLUSION

When the radar chart equates that of sine wave with single value , we have attained true immortality. Kindly provide your valuable feedback on these graphs if it had been thought provoking. This paper is a product of the dream to live longer and is the 1st attempt using some line and radar graphs.

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